

Theoretical and CFD analysis of gravity and galaxy formation and rotation in a dilatant vacuum.

Marco Fedi*

Ministero dell'Istruzione, dell'Università e della Ricerca (MIUR), Rome, Italy

Mario R. L. Artigiani†

Engineering3D.it, Desenzano del Garda, Italy

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Following some successful computations in which the vacuum has been treated as a non-Newtonian dilatant fluid, to solve the perihelion precession of the planet Mercury and to obtain a better solution for the Pioneer anomaly, in this study we proceed with describing gravity, both at micro- and macro-level, as well as galaxy formation, shape and rotation, still according to a dilatant vacuum, also by means of high-resolution computational fluid dynamics simulations. We show that the gravitational model is compatible with general relativity and we obtain various galaxy shapes, along with the flat-profile of rotation velocity, without resorting to dark matter. These further evidences seem to confirm that physical vacuum is a dilatant quantum fluid, probably a hydrodynamic feature of the viscous Higgs field.

Keywords: dilatant vacuum, quantum gravity, spin, galaxy formation, flat profile

Introduction

After hundreds of experiments ruled out the existence of the luminiferous ether ([1–5] and the following, up to [6, 7]), i.e. of a medium which was supposed to fill up all space, the most accredited approach to gravity remains general relativity (GR), which treats space as a mathematical entity, through differential geometry, despite this strategy remains unsuccessful after more than a century, as far as the achievement of a quantum theory of gravity is concerned. Paradoxically, the physics of gravity seems to have entered a blind alley from exactly the beginning of GR, a wonderful and long alley but nevertheless blind: GR has problems with the dark part of the universe, i.e. with 95% of it, dark stuff [8, 9] that we cannot directly detect but whose effects are observed and known. Galaxy observations refute GR, because a flat profile of the rotation velocity curve is detected, whereas this should not be the case. Thus, the geometric Einsteinian space-time was filled up with something less mathematical and more physical: dark matter [10, 11]. We must admit that there is something in empty space, despite the failure of the ether-drift tests to detect it. In 1920, Einstein himself was disappointed and declared [12]: “according to the general theory of relativity space is endowed with physical qualities; in this sense, therefore, there exists an aether. According to the general theory of relativity space without aether is unthinkable”. Previously, he was indeed influenced by the null result of the Michelson-Morley experiment [1, 2], which suggested that space was really empty. Nowadays, the physics of the dark sector says that Einstein in 1920 was right: without a substance scattered throughout space his theory is “physically” unthinkable: what deforms? A merely mathematical space? Deformation or rather pressure gradients in a fluid space? Aerospace engineers are well aware of analogies between fluid dynamics

and differential geometry. We need a more physical theory of gravity, by treating space as a real medium, endowed with true hydrodynamic features. What features are these? Previous studies have successfully shown that the vacuum behaves as a non-Newtonian, shear-thickening (dilatant) fluid [13]. In this way the Pioneer anomaly has been correctly solved with much more precision and simplicity than the currently accepted explanation based on thermal simulations and, in the same study, Einstein formula for the precession of perihelia was directly rederived from the equation of dilatant vacuum. Also relativistic kinetic energy was revealed [14] as the further energy that is necessary to accelerate a body whose inertia increases with speed due to the reaction of the shear-thickening vacuum, whose viscosity curve obeys the Lorentz factor, reinterpreted as the rheogram of the vacuum. Contrary to what one might believe, a dilatant vacuum does not cause observable decay of planetary orbits, since the equations show [13] that the orbital decay remains negligible over trillions of years, due to the large masses of the planets on which vacuum’s viscous force (F_0) acts, as deducible from the Newtonian relation $a = F_0/m$. Physical vacuum as a dilatant fluid seems to be a more powerful approach than superfluid vacuum theory ([15–17]), whose recent evolution is the logarithmic BEC vacuum theory [18, 19]. Vacuum superfluidity only occurs within a non-relativistic regime, moving away from which *dilatancy* prevails, following the mathematical law of the Lorentz factor. In the present study we show, via high-resolution computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations, that a dilatant vacuum can lead to gravity quantization and to the correct formation and rotation of galaxies, also justifying their various shapes. But what about the problem concerning the non-detectable ether? Our simulations help understanding that under specific hydrodynamic conditions (e.g. the presence of a porous medium) the ether wind is neutralized and undetectable.

In this study we want to approach the issue of quantum gravity by replacing the concept of curvature with that of pressure in a fluid, dilatant space. We show that this approach is able to justify the relativistic effects of GR and also produces

* E-mail: marco.fedi@istruzione.it

† E-mail: artigiani@engineering3d.it

a correct model for spiral galaxy formation, shapes and behavior, i.e. correct rotation without the addition of dark matter in the model. This study starts from Gauss' law for gravity (Sec. I), in which we consider a *real* flow of fluid vacuum; we then give explanation for the incoming flux by describing its mechanism at a microscopic level, via the Bernoulli force exerted by massive particles as quantized vortices in the fluid vacuum (Sect. II); in Sect. III we obtain a formula for gravity without the Newtonian constant G , revealing that, as many constants of physics, its role was that of adjusting units and quantities (in a non-quantum formula): once we consider pressure and density of the vacuum, instead of mass and distance, the units of the gravitational potential are immediately correct, as shown in Eq. (17); after that, the quantum aspects of the new formula are analyzed in Sect. IV; in the following section (V) we suggest a justification to the failure of the ether-drift tests, via CFD simulations, by analyzing a flow through a porous medium; in Sect. VI we reason that a dilatant vacuum is the ideal propagation medium for light, as it can justify its transverse propagation and its very high frequencies: a description of photon as a transverse phonon through the dilatant vacuum's quasi-lattice is proposed; in the following section (VII) an alternative hydrodynamic version of the field equation is suggested and in Sect. VIII we successfully test the model, as in [13], by exactly computing the anomalous perihelion precession of the planet Mercury; in Sect. IX we do not forget to justify also gravitational waves as a hydrodynamic phenomenon, i.e. as negative pressure waves through a liquid space, and in Sect. X we finally simulate the birth of different kinds of galaxies, driven by the black holes in the galaxy core; from the simulations, which include a film, a correct flat profile of the rotation velocity curve emerges (XI), along with an unexpected *breath* of galaxies (Sect. XII).

I. The starting point: Gauss's law for gravity

Gauss's law for gravity reads

$$\mathbf{F}_g = \int_S \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{r}) \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{r}) dS. \quad (1)$$

For our approach it is much more convenient than Newton's law, because it describes the gravitational field as a flow entering into a spherical volume. We start by hypothesizing that this flow is a real flow of fluid, dilatant vacuum.

II. Cause of the flow at microscopical level: spin-generated Bernoulli force as the engine of gravity.

Dilatant vacuum can be interpreted as a superfluid (dark energy) doped with scattered dark-matter particles (which together make up $\sim 95\%$ of the mass-energy of the universe), something like a cosmic oobleck [20]. At the same time, vacuum dilatancy can be also interpreted as a hydrodynamic feature of the viscous Higgs field. The temperature of superfluid dark energy at 2.72K, i.e. that of the cosmic microwave background (CMB), would match that of laboratory superfluids. In superfluids, quantized vortices

FIG. 1. Above: gravitational field as pressure gradient in a fluid quantum vacuum, which obeys the inverse-square law. Below: velocity field due to the pressure gradient. Pressure and velocity scales are arbitrary.

spontaneously arise and since a vortex tube must extend to a boundary or close in a loop (an interesting connection with loop quantum gravity [21] can be seen in this fact), obeying Helmholtz's second principle, vortex rings (vortex tori) can spontaneously form in a doped superfluid vacuum (Fig 2) [16, 17, 22]. A toroidal vortex would correspond to a fundamental fermion if the ratio of toroidal to poloidal rotations were 1/2 (representing spin $\frac{1}{2}$). Any other kind of spin can be obtained considering different ratios. Let us analyze the fundamental equations of what above described. Considering physical vacuum as a doped Bose-Einstein condensate (BEC), we start from the Gross-Pitaevskii equation (GPE) to analyze its hydrodynamic behavior [23]

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi + g\psi |\psi|^2 - \psi \mu_0 \quad (2)$$

where ψ is the condensate wave function, m the mass of a quantum of the fluid vacuum, μ_0 the chemical potential and

FIG. 2. A vortex line with healing length ξ , actually a vortex tube, closes in a circle, becoming a vortex torus. Below: the Möbius-strip trajectory of a vacuum's quantum in the vortex torus: the quantum returns to its start position after a 720° rotation of the torus. Below on the right-hand side, we can see, as a further example, the paths of 12 quanta. The ratio rotations/revolutions corresponds to spin.

$g = 4\pi a \hbar^2 / m$ a low-energy parameter, where a represents the scattering length between vacuum's quanta. In the phase representation $\psi = \sqrt{\rho_0} e^{i\varphi}$, $\rho_0 = |\psi|^2$ is vacuum's density. From (2) we can write the continuity equation and the analogue of the Euler equation

$$\frac{\partial \rho_0}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{v}_S) = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$m \left(\frac{\partial \rho_0}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v}_S \cdot \nabla \right) \mathbf{v}_S = \nabla \left(\mu_0 - g\rho + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_0}}{\sqrt{\rho_0}} \right) \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_S = \frac{\hbar}{m} \nabla \varphi$ is the superfluid velocity and

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_0}}{\sqrt{\rho_0}} \quad (5)$$

the quantum potential. The condensate must be a continuous function in space, so its phase is continuous modulo 2π . We define the quantized circulation (Γ) with the line integral

$$\oint_C d\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{v}_S = \frac{2\pi \hbar}{m} n \equiv \Gamma \quad (n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots) \quad (6)$$

where C is a close loop in space, encircling a vortex line, $\psi = 0$, and the superfluid's density vanishes. The

problem of ultraviolet divergence and of the radius of the fundamental particles is solved in this approach by not considering point-particles but toroidal vortices of vacuum's quanta, whose radius is $r = 2\xi$, with ξ defined as the healing length,

$$\xi \equiv \sqrt{\frac{V}{8\pi a N}}, \quad (7)$$

where V is the volume in which the vortex arises, a the scattering length and N a normalized number of vacuum's quanta in the volume. The ratio of the velocities v_1 and v_2 of vacuum's quanta in the vortex (Fig. 2) satisfactorily represents all spin numbers. A hydrodynamic reformulation of the Barut-Zanghi theory [24], which includes spin, was proposed by Salesi and Recami, who suggested [25], similarly to us, that quantum potential

$$Q = -\frac{1}{2} m \vec{v}_S^2 - \frac{1}{2} \nabla \cdot \vec{v}_S \quad (8)$$

(in natural units, $\hbar = 1$) totally arises from a particle's internal motion $\vec{v}_S \times \vec{s}$, where

$$\vec{v}_S = \frac{1}{2m} \rho^{-1} \nabla \rho = \frac{1}{2m} \frac{\nabla R^2}{R^2}, \quad (9)$$

being \vec{s} the direction of spin. The link to the concept of vortex-particle is, in this way, quite immediate. If, to complete a turn in the poloidal direction, a quantum in the vortex needs the same time the vortex needs to complete two turns in the toroidal direction, then the vortex has spin $1/2$ (fermion), i.e. the system returns to the same state after a 720° rotation and after each quantum in the vortex has traveled along a Möbius-strip path (Fig. 2). By defining ω_1, ω_2 as the angular velocities (toroidal and poloidal), the spin angular momentum (S) is determined by the ratio $\omega_1 / \omega_2 = (n\pi / dt) / (2\pi / dt)$ and after the cancellations

$$\frac{\omega_1}{\omega_2} = \frac{n}{2} = S. \quad (10)$$

Spin-0 vortices may arise through a further evolution of the torus into a spheroidal vortex. The parametric equation defining the position of a quantum in the torus vortex is expressed as

$$\begin{cases} x = (r + \xi \cos(\omega_1 dt + \phi_0)) \cos(\omega_2 dt + \theta_0) \\ y = (r + \xi \cos(\omega_1 dt + \phi_0)) \sin(\omega_2 dt + \theta_0) \\ z = \xi \sin(\omega_1 dt + \phi_0) \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where $r \geq 2\xi$ is the distance between the centers of the tube and of the torus, $\omega_1 = d\phi/dt$, $\omega_2 = d\theta/dt$ and ϕ_0 and θ_0 are phases with arbitrary values between 0 and 2π .

The toroidal shape of fundamental particles also resembles the loops of Loop Quantum Gravity [21, 26] but in our case on a higher scale to describe, for instance, a fundamental fermion. At the same time, we can also notice a certain similarity between vortex lines and string theory. Vacuum's hydrodynamics has in our opinion the potential to reconcile

different approaches into a single model. Vortex chirality represents matter-antimatter parity and an opportune change in the ratio ω_1/ω_2 would transform a boson into a fermion, or vice versa: such a mechanism could be therefore important in better understanding the foundations of supersymmetry.

It is known that quantum vortices exert Bernoulli force, generating attractive or repulsive forces [17, 27]. In particular, Pshenichnyuk proved that vortices in a doped superfluid behave differently compared to those in a standard superfluid [27]. The correct attractive or repulsive force, obeying an inverse-square law, is observed in doped superfluids. The kinetic energy density acting on the dopant's particles, caused by the velocity fields of the superfluid vortices can be written as

$$K^{++} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_Q} \frac{\psi_\infty^2 (4R^2 + d^2 - 4Rd \cos \alpha)}{(R^2 + \xi^2)(R^2 + d^2 + \xi^2 - 2Rd \cos \alpha)}, \quad (12)$$

$$K^{+-} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_Q} \frac{\psi_\infty^2 d^2}{(R^2 + \xi^2)(R^2 + d^2 + \xi^2 - 2Rd \cos \alpha)}, \quad (13)$$

where $++/+ -$ signs refer to same or different topological charges denoting repulsion or attraction, d is the distance between the vortices, R the radius of a doping particle, ξ the healing length and α the azimuthal angle in cylindrical coordinates which is associated with the doping particle. This mechanism is driven by Bernoulli force, whose equation is

$$\mathbf{F}_b = \int_S \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{r}) \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{r}) dS \quad (14)$$

where $K(\mathbf{r}) = \rho v^2/2$ expresses the kinetic energy density, which dominates on the vortex surface, while the density of the superfluid drops to zero within the healing length, and $\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{r})$ is a unit vector, normal to the surface S , over which the integral is calculated. Bernoulli force arises in superfluids as a superposition of the velocity fields of the vortices. Points where the fields reinforce each other and where their interaction makes them weaker produce a pressure-related Bernoulli effect. We notice that (14) mathematically equals Gauss's law for gravity (1) and also Coulomb's law is equivalent to Gauss's law for the electric field, hence again to the Bernoulli force. To conclude this section, three points are therefore of primary importance:

1. the necessity of a *doped* superfluid, as in the dilatant-vacuum model, to obtain the correct attraction/repulsion forces between vortices.
2. the mathematical identity between Bernoulli force and Gauss's laws for gravity and electromagnetism.
3. gravity as an emergent hydrodynamic force coinciding with the Bernoulli force exerted by vortex-particles (by spin, described as internal motion of particles)

In short, the equation for gravity (1) *is the expression of the Bernoulli force* (14) and this can lead, as discussed below, to the quantization of gravity. Of course, also macroscopic bodies, such as a planet, which consist of vortex-particles, produce a pressure gradient around them

in the fluid dilatant vacuum, which is called gravitational field (Fig. 1). It is interesting to consider that toroidal vortices, whose rotations conflict, annihilate if they come into contact: matter-antimatter annihilation would be then easily explained in hydrodynamical terms and the photons emitted are actually phonons in the dilatant vacuum (Sect. VI), which transversally propagate at very high frequency, due to the shear-thickening feature of the vacuum. This analogously to the observed phonon emission as quantum vortices annihilate in superfluid helium.

III. Equation of quantum gravity without Newton's constant.

The macroscopic Bernoulli effect, detectable as the gravitational field of large bodies, is thence a pressure gradient which causes acceleration toward the center of the massive object, according to the known hydrodynamic law

$$\vec{a} = -\vec{\nabla} \frac{P}{\rho} \quad (15)$$

where P is the pressure and ρ the density of the fluid. Applying (15) to dilatant vacuum (denoted by the subscript \emptyset) we can write the expression for the gravitational field, where gravity is a hydrodynamic force

$$\vec{g} = -\vec{\nabla} \frac{P_\emptyset}{\rho_\emptyset} \quad (16)$$

It is fundamental to notice that, in this new expression of the gravitational field, the Newtonian constant of gravitation disappears. Here we compare the formulas (with units) of the classical and quantum (Sect. IV) gravitational potential

$$V = -G \frac{M}{r} \left[\frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}^2} \right] \Leftrightarrow V_Q = -\frac{P_\emptyset}{\rho_\emptyset} \left[\frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}^2} \right]. \quad (17)$$

Often in physics the presence of a constant refers to the necessity of adjusting the scale and the units of measure. In this case, Newton's formula for universal gravitation resorts to quantities such as mass and distance but these are not directly involved in quantum gravity, which requires to consider pressure and density of the vacuum: in this way there is no longer need for the Newtonian constant G (17). The fact that such a constant is used by Einstein in GR underlines a limitation of the theory, which is not indeed a quantum theory of gravitation. After a century from GR and considering the limitations of the geometrical approach to gravity, the time is now ripe, in our opinion, to switch to pressure in a fluid vacuum, as a hydrodynamic process occurring over time, instead of curvature in a mathematical spacetime. By replacing the new expression for the gravitational field \vec{g} (16) in the formula of gravitation $\vec{F}_g = -m\vec{g}$, we directly obtain the equation of quantum gravity

$$\vec{F}_g = -m\vec{\nabla} \frac{P_\emptyset}{\rho_\emptyset} \quad (18)$$

IV. Quantum aspects

The classical gravitational potential energy $U = -GMm/r$ becomes then

$$U_Q = -m \frac{P_0}{\rho_0}. \quad (19)$$

Let us demonstrate that U_Q is the quantum potential of (18). We first express (19) by resorting to momentum

$$U_Q = -m \frac{P_0}{\rho_0} = -\|\mathbf{p}\| \cdot \|\mathbf{u}\| = -\frac{\|\mathbf{p}\|^2}{m}, \quad (20)$$

where $\|\mathbf{u}\| = \|\mathbf{p}\|/m$. From (20), switching to the momentum operator, we can write a time-independent, one-dimensional, eigenvalue Schrödinger equation (SE)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\hat{p}^2}{m} \psi &= -\frac{\hbar^2}{m} \nabla^2 \psi = -\frac{\hbar^2}{m} \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) \psi = \\ &= \hat{V}(r) \psi \stackrel{(\hat{T}\psi=0)}{=} \hat{H} \psi = E \psi, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

considering no initial velocity. The expectation value for the gravitational potential energy is

$$\langle E \rangle = \frac{\langle p^2 \rangle}{m} = \int_0^\infty \psi^* \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{m} \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) \right] \psi dr. \quad (22)$$

The velocity field associated with the pressure field generated by the vortex-particles (grouped for instance in a macroscopic massive object), via Bernoulli force (14), in the fluid dilatant vacuum acts as a pilot wave in the vacuum, driving any particle through the gravitational field. For this reason it may be useful to resort to Madelung's quantum hydrodynamic approach. Let us perform polar decomposition of the wavefunction, $\psi = \sqrt{\rho_0} e^{i\hbar^{-1}S}$, being S the phase. By replacing into the SE and introducing time dependency, we obtain the Madelung equations, that is the continuity equation

$$\partial_t \rho_0 + \frac{1}{m} \nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \nabla S) = 0, \quad (23)$$

describing the flow of vacuum's quanta along the current in the fluid vacuum, produced by the Bernoulli effect, and the Hamilton-Jacobi equation

$$\partial_t S = -\frac{1}{2m} (\nabla S)^2 - V(r) - Q, \quad (24)$$

where

$$Q = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_0}}{\sqrt{\rho_0}} \quad (25)$$

is the quantum potential. Since we are considering no initial velocity and no classical potential (being the gravitational potential explained through the described quantum picture), the action S over time, i.e. the acceleration of a particle in the velocity field, reduces to

$$\partial_t S = -Q. \quad (26)$$

FIG. 3. By applying horizontal wind to the radial inflow (1), the directions of the field vectors are influenced and perfect radiality is lost.

Thus the hydrodynamic interpretation of the classical gravitational potential corresponds to double the quantum potential, expressed in units of energy

$$U_Q = -m \frac{P_0}{\rho_0} = 2Q = -\frac{\hbar^2}{m} \frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_0}}{\sqrt{\rho_0}}, \quad (27)$$

and (18) can be simplified to

$$\mathbf{F}_{g(Q)} = 2\nabla Q, \quad (28)$$

as double the corresponding quantum force (∇Q), which can be expressed in function of the quantum pressure tensor \mathbf{p}_Q , where pressure in a dilatant quantum vacuum replaces the curvature of Einstein's geometrical space-time, specifically the curvature expressed by the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - 2^{-1}g_{\mu\nu}R$, of the field equations, where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor and R the scalar curvature. Resorting to the quantum pressure tensor, quantum gravity can be expressed as a hydrodynamic quantum force in a dilatant quantum vacuum

$$\mathbf{F}_{g(Q)} = -\frac{2m}{\rho_m} \nabla \cdot \left[-\left(\frac{\hbar}{2m} \right)^2 \rho_m \nabla \otimes \nabla \ln \rho_m \right], \quad (29)$$

where $\rho_m = m\rho$ is mass density.

V. An old question in a new light

We are aware that any attempt to treat space as a fluid clashes with the result of hundreds of ether-drift tests. However, our simulations show that specific conditions, not considered

before, can reconcile the existence of a dilatant fluid that pervades all space with the fact that detecting the effect of the ether wind due to the motion of the Earth through space has never been possible.

At first instance, if a fluid vacuum exists then also the lines of an electric or magnetic field can be interpreted as the result of pressure and velocity fields in the vacuum, acting as pilot waves for virtual photons, i.e. for the quanta of the electromagnetic interaction. In this picture, one can hypothesize that the Earth's magnetic field and even the magnetic bubble on the edge of the heliosphere, may deflect the ether wind allowing the null result of the Michelson-Morley experiment and of the subsequent ether-drift tests. This could be possible by thinking of the fluid vacuum as a sea of virtual electric dipoles (particle-antiparticle pairs) which interact with the magnetic field via the Lorentz force. The dipole consists of two opposite charges at an arbitrary short distance d . The Lorentz force reduces in this case to

$$\vec{F} = q(\vec{v} \times \vec{B}), \quad (30)$$

where $\vec{v} = (\vec{v}_1 + \vec{v}_2)/2$ the average velocity of the charges. The total force can be written

$$p\vec{v} \times \frac{\vec{B}(\vec{r} + \vec{p}/q) - \vec{B}(\vec{r}, t)}{d} \quad (31)$$

and as d goes to zero but q goes to infinity, we have

$$p\vec{v} \times (\hat{d} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (32)$$

which equals

$$\vec{v} \times (\vec{p} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}(\vec{r}, t), \quad (33)$$

expressing the magnetic force on the dipole which re-orient it along the lines of the magnetic field. In this case, the Earth's magnetic field would act as a shield for the ether wind, that is for the flow of virtual electric dipoles in the fluid quantum vacuum, as it also does for charges which are transported by the solar wind.

Also the gravitational field itself, as an inflow of fluid quantum vacuum [28, 29], would deflect the ether wind, whose velocity would be added to that of the gravitational flow: however, this fact would deform the gravitational field (Fig. 3), so a different mechanism has to be at stake to justify the non-detectability of the apparent ether flow, despite the existence of a fluid space. For instance, it is interesting to also consider the effect of a porous medium on the ether wind. As our simulations show, if the ether flow passed through a porous medium, scattered in the gravitational field, it would slow down and re-orient along the lines of the field (as shown in Fig. 5), as if the Earth were immobile in the fluid vacuum, justifying the null result of the ether-drift experiments. The porous medium might be represented by the Earth's atmosphere, a low-density medium that would let part of the ether wind pass, slow down and re-orient, while a part of it would be attracted by the Bernoulli force

FIG. 4. When the gravitational flow passes through a porous medium it remains radial despite the presence of a horizontal flow playing the role of the ether wind. Furthermore, within the porous region, also the velocity of the field, besides its radiality, remains unaffected. This means that if the Earth were surrounded by such a medium (e.g. its atmosphere), any ether-drift test would yield null result. In the picture we see that the pressure field remains radial until the radius exits the porous region, out of which the gravitational field tends to take the form of a cardioid.

field of the molecules in the atmosphere. At this point we suggest to repeat the Michelson-Morley experience in the interplanetary space. Mars is not recommended for the presence of an atmosphere, albeit very rarefied, and of strong crustal magnetic fields. In conclusion, we think there are valid reasons to consider a re-orientation and a deceleration of the ether wind during its journey to the Earth's surface.

VI. Light in dilatant vacuum: the ideal medium.

Starting from the speed of sound in a dilatant fluid, $v_s = \sqrt{S/\rho}$, where S is the shear modulus and ρ the density of the fluid, we rewrite it using shear compliance $j = S^{-1}$ and we reinterpret vacuum permeability μ_0 and permittivity ϵ_0 as density ρ_0 and shear compliance j_0 (respectively) of dilatant vacuum. Thus

$$c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu_0 \epsilon_0}} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{\rho_0 j_0}}, \quad (34)$$

FIG. 5. Same situation as in Fig. 4 but showing the velocity field instead of the pressure field. The black circle delimits the porous region. To be precise, this area should gradually fade out without showing a clear boundary: the aim of this simulation is however highlighting the re-orientation and the slowing down of the ether wind once it enters a porous medium, which evens the ether flow.

FIG. 6. Once the apparent flow of fluid vacuum, caused by the motion of the Earth and of the solar system through the liquid space, enters the porous area (the Earth's atmosphere?), the incoming vectors of the gravitational field re-orient and become virtually radial, so no ether wind can be detected on the Earth, justifying the failure of all tests aimed to detecting such a wind.

It is very interesting to notice that wave propagation through a dilatant fluid allows transverse waves, such as light, and it also allows propagation at very high frequencies, again in agreement with the behavior of light. Gremaud [30] states that Maxwell's equations can be seen as a special case of deformation of a solid lattice: dilatant vacuum appears to be then the ideal medium for light propagation. In short, in the dilatant vacuum's quasi-lattice, a photon is nothing but a transverse phonon. This interpretation is in agreement with all equations and effects concerning photons: both photons and phonons are bosons [31]; identical excitations can be created by repeatedly applying the creation operator, b^\dagger ; both possess wave-particle duality [32, 33], indeed in a lattice, or quasi-lattice we expect that waves appear that behave like particles; they obey the doppler effect, $z = (f_{emit} - f_{obs}) / f_{obs}$; they are symmetric under exchange, $|\alpha, \beta\rangle = |\beta, \alpha\rangle$; they possess a pseudo-momentum, where that of a phonon is $p_{ph} \equiv \hbar k = h/\lambda$, with $k = 2\pi/\lambda$; they are involved in the photoelectric effect and in the Compton scattering, thanks to their momentum; they can spin [34, 35]. As far as spin is concerned, it would be realistic that the higher degree of freedom of a phonon in the quasi-lattice of a fluid medium, allowed it to possess spin 1. For this reason, in this study, photons are treated as special spin-1 phonons in the quasi-lattice of dilatant vacuum. We actually know that photon spin can have three different values (-1, 0, 1), so, at most, magnitude 1. Circular phonons have been described in [36] and rotating phonons also arise in the physics of nanotubes [37]. Photons and phonons can form squeezed coherent states [38] and they can interact via parametric down conversion [39]. For both, $\hbar\omega/2$ is vacuum's contribution, since the harmonic oscillator eigenvalues for the mode ω_k (k is the wave number) are $E_n = (n + 1/2)\hbar\omega_k$, with $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, and (to confirm the presence of a *false* vacuum) even for $n = 0$ the energy is not zero. Both photons and phonons can eventually form non-diffracting waves [40]. We conclude by affirming that in our opinion a photon is actually a transverse phonon propagating through the quasi-lattice of a dilatant vacuum.

VII. Hydrodynamic analogous of the field equation

By resorting to (19), (27) and (34), the field equation can be rewritten in terms of a fluid, dilatant vacuum, where pressure replaces the mathematical concept of curvature

$$\mathcal{G}_{\mu\nu} = -8\pi \frac{r}{M} P_\emptyset j_\emptyset \rho_\emptyset (1 - j_\emptyset T^{\mu\nu}) = -4\pi R_{S\emptyset} \frac{\rho_\emptyset}{M} (1 - j_\emptyset T^{\mu\nu}), \quad (35)$$

where $R_{S\emptyset} = 2P_\emptyset j_\emptyset r$ is the quantum-hydrodynamic Schwarzschild radius. The T^{00} component of the stress-energy tensor is the density of the fluid vacuum, T^{ii} refers to vacuum's pressure, $T^{0i} = T^{i0}$ is momentum density, T^{ik} is momentum flux, which is also related to vacuum's viscosity, whereas the remaining components T^{ik} (with $i \neq k$) refer to shear stress in the shear-thickening

FIG. 7. CFD simulations for the Lense-Thirring effect, where space-time distortion is replaced by a distorted pressure field in a fluid, dilatant vacuum.

vacuum. The Schwarzschild solution therefore reads

$$ds^2 = (1 - 2P_\theta(r)j_\theta) \frac{1}{\rho_\theta j_\theta} dt^2 - \frac{1}{1 - 2P_\theta(r)j_\theta} dr^2 - r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2). \quad (36)$$

In this case $\gamma(\tau) = (t(\tau), r(\tau), \theta(\tau), \phi(\tau))$, with τ the proper time, is a geodesic if

$$\begin{cases} \ddot{i} + \frac{2P_\theta j_\theta}{r-R_{S0}} \dot{i} \dot{r} = 0 \\ \ddot{r} + \frac{P_\theta j_\theta (r-R_{S0})}{r^2} \dot{i}^2 - \frac{P_\theta j_\theta}{r-R_{S0}} \dot{r}^2 - (r-R_{S0}) [\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\phi}^2] = 0 \\ \ddot{\theta} + \frac{2\dot{r}}{r} \dot{\theta} - \sin \theta \cos \theta \dot{\phi}^2 = 0 \\ \ddot{\phi} + \frac{2\dot{r}}{r} \dot{\phi} + \frac{2}{\tan \theta} \dot{\phi} \dot{\theta} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

The quantum hydrodynamic equivalents of the non-null components of the curvature tensor are

$$\begin{aligned} R_{0303} &= -(1 - 2P_\theta j_\theta) \frac{P_\theta}{\rho_\theta} \sin^2 \theta = \\ &= -(1 - 2P_\theta j_\theta) \frac{2Q}{m} \sin^2 \theta = \\ &= (1 - 2P_\theta j_\theta) \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2} \frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_\theta}}{\sqrt{\rho_\theta}} \sin^2 \theta \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

$$R_{1313} = \frac{P_\theta r}{\rho_\theta \left(\rho_\theta j_\theta + 2 \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2} \frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_\theta}}{\sqrt{\rho_\theta}} r \right)} \sin^2 \theta \quad (39)$$

$$R_{0202} = (1 - 2P_\theta j_\theta) \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2} \frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_\theta}}{\sqrt{\rho_\theta}} \quad (40)$$

$$R_{1212} = \frac{P_\theta r}{\rho_\theta \left(\rho_\theta j_\theta + 2 \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2} \frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_\theta}}{\sqrt{\rho_\theta}} r \right)} \quad (41)$$

$$R_{2323} = -r - R_{S0} \sin^2 \theta \quad (42)$$

$$R_{0101} = -2 \frac{P_\theta}{\rho_\theta} = -\frac{4Q}{m} = 2 \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2} \frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_\theta}}{\sqrt{\rho_\theta}}. \quad (43)$$

Apparent acceleration with respect to a stationary observer is given by

$$\begin{aligned} a_a &= \frac{P_\theta}{\rho_\theta} \frac{1}{r} (1 + P_\theta j_\theta) = \frac{2Q}{m} \frac{1}{r} (1 + P_\theta j_\theta) = \\ &= \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2} \frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_\theta}}{\sqrt{\rho_\theta}} \frac{1}{r} (1 + P_\theta j_\theta). \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

The radius of a circular orbit is

$$\begin{aligned} R &= \frac{L^2}{P_\theta} \frac{\rho_\theta}{rm} - 3P_\theta j_\theta r = \\ &= \frac{L^2}{r} \frac{m}{\hbar^2} \frac{\sqrt{\rho_\theta}}{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_\theta}} - 3P_\theta j_\theta r. \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

And light deflection angle due to a pressure gradient in the liquid vacuum (due to a gravitational field) is

$$\delta \phi = 4P_\theta j_\theta. \quad (46)$$

Obviously, since we have described a photon as a transverse phonon in the quasi-lattice of the dilatant vacuum (Sect. VI) the direction of propagation of the phonon is influenced by the pressure gradients in the fluid vacuum (i.e. by gravitational fields, according to GR). When the speed of the incoming flow (Fig. 1), due to a sufficiently high mass density, is equal or greater than the speed of the phonon, light cannot propagate and we observe a black hole.

The gravitational redshift is expressed in terms of pressure and shear compliance of the dilatant vacuum

$$z \approx 1 + P_\theta j_\theta \quad (47)$$

and the Unruh temperature

$$T_{Unruh} = \frac{\hbar a \sqrt{\rho_\theta j_\theta}}{2\pi k_B} \quad (48)$$

by resorting to density and shear compliance of the vacuum. It is particularly important to include the Unruh effect in a theory of quantum gravity [41]: the friction due to motion through a dilatant space can easily justify this effect.

Let us now express Kerr metric in quantum hydrodynamic terms. As we have seen above, $GM/r = P_\theta/\rho_\theta$ and $c = 1/\sqrt{\rho_\theta j_\theta}$. Let us shorten the equation putting $a = J/M_d$, where J is angular momentum and M_d is a mass which is discontinuous in density (if not macroscopically at least at a microscopic level), since this condition is necessary in our simulations, where the discontinuities act as a sort of junction points to distort vacuum's pressure field (or to distort space-time in Einstein's geometrical model). Still to shorten,

we also put $b = 1 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta / r^2$. Kerr metric then reads

$$\begin{aligned}
ds^2 = & - \left(1 - \frac{2P_0 j_0}{b} \right) \frac{1}{\rho_0 j_0} dt^2 - \frac{4P_0 j_0 a \sin^2 \theta}{b} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\rho_0 j_0}} dt d\phi + \\
& + \frac{b}{1 + \frac{a^2}{r^2} - 2P_0 j_0} dr^2 + (r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta) d\theta^2 + \\
& + \left(r^2 + a^2 + \frac{2P_0 j_0 a^2 \sin^2 \theta}{b} \sin^2 \theta \right) \theta d\phi^2.
\end{aligned} \tag{49}$$

Also this equation says that space-time curvature is actually a pressure gradient in a fluid space. Which in this case can be distorted, if the body into which the flow is directed is rotating (Fig. 7). The issue of density inhomogeneity in the rotating mass is crucial. We think that the Kerr solution to the field equations cannot actually correspond to a real, observed natural phenomenon as long as it describes an homogeneous, isotropic rotating body. Indeed, our simulations indicate that in the Kerr solution the rotating mass has to possess a heterogeneous density, even if slight and at microscopic level (atoms and molecules as a non-continuous matter distribution), as it is after all the natural case of all material bodies. In fact the simulations exclude that a perfectly isotropic (continuous mass distribution in space) rotating body can distort the space-time or analogously, in our model, that it can distort the pressure field and velocity field around a massive body. We have obtained the Lense-Thirring effect in our simulations by introducing density discontinuities (Fig. 7). This theoretical detail should be in our opinion incorporated in the mathematics of the Kerr solution to let it actually correspond to the observations. For this reason we specify M_d (where the subscript d means discontinuous) in the parameter a of Eq. (49).

VIII. Testing the theory with the relativistic precession of perihelia

To prove that in a correct theory of quantum gravity the concept of space-time curvature has to be replaced by pressure gradients in a fluid, dilatant vacuum and by other features of such a vacuum, as for instance its viscosity, it has been demonstrated [13] that the first classical test of GR, the perihelion precession of Mercury, can be exactly solved with the dilatant vacuum approach. Let us consider the modified Stokes equation for dilatant vacuum [13] expressing the non-linear viscous force of the vacuum

$$F_{vac} = -6\pi r(\gamma - 1)\kappa = -6\pi r \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} - 1 \right) \kappa \tag{50}$$

where κ is a unitary constant expressed in $\text{Kg} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$. Let us define

$$D = \gamma - 1 \tag{51}$$

as a dimensionless term of vacuum dilatancy which obeys the Lorentz factor, here interpreted as the rheogram of

the vacuum, whose asymptote corresponds to vacuum solidification under shear stress. Let us consider the relativistic formula for perihelion precession in three variants

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{24\pi^3 a^2}{T^2(1-e^2)c^2} = 6\pi \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2 \frac{1}{1-e^2} = 6\pi \frac{GM}{a(1-e^2)c^2} \tag{52}$$

where $\Delta\phi$ expresses the relativistic contribution to perihelion precession in radians per revolution and the expression in the center is obtained using $T^2 = 4\pi^2 a^2 / v^2$, i.e. resorting to mean orbital velocity, whereas in the expression on the right the stable second cosmic velocity, $v = \sqrt{GM/r}$, is used. The dimensionless norm of Eq. (50) is

$$6\pi \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} - 1 \right) = 6\pi(\gamma - 1) \tag{53}$$

whose result can be expressed in radians. Using the approximation

$$2(\gamma - 1) \approx \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2 \tag{54}$$

Eq. (53) now reads

$$3\pi \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2 = 3\pi \frac{GM}{ac^2} \tag{55}$$

We use then the elliptic parameter, since the orbit is elliptical, replacing a with $a(1-e^2)$ and we obtain a formula which exactly gives 1/2 the result of GR (52)

$$\Delta\phi = 3\pi \frac{GM}{a(1-e^2)c^2} = 3\pi \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2 \frac{1}{1-e^2} \tag{56}$$

This result is the precession occurring in a semi-orbit due to the use of mean orbital velocity $v = (v_{max}/2) + (v_{min}/2)$. The full precession (52) is therefore given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta\phi &= 3\pi \left(\frac{v_{max}}{c}\right)^2 \frac{1}{1-e^2} + 3\pi \left(\frac{v_{min}}{c}\right)^2 \frac{1}{1-e^2} = \\
&= 6\pi \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2 \frac{1}{1-e^2}
\end{aligned} \tag{57}$$

where v_{max} and v_{min} , each referring to a semi-orbit, recombine into the mean orbital velocity v . By summarizing the steps above, the formula can be written as follows

$$\Delta\phi \equiv \left\| \frac{2F_{vac}}{\kappa r(1-e^2)} \right\| = 12\pi \frac{D}{(1-e^2)} \tag{58}$$

By testing it with the parameters of Mercury, we see that *it exactly gives the well-known value of GR*

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta\phi &= 12\pi \frac{D}{(1-e^2)} = 12\pi \frac{\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{GM}{ac^2}\right)} - 1} \right)}{(1-e^2)} = \\
&= 12\pi \frac{\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{(6.67408 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-2})(1.98847 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg})}{(5.7909 \times 10^{10} \text{ m})(299792458 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1})^2}} - 1} \right)}{1 - 0.20563^2} \right)}{1 - 0.20563^2} = \\
&= 5.018649 \times 10^{-7} \text{ rad/rev.} \Rightarrow 42.98''/\text{century}
\end{aligned} \tag{59}$$

FIG. 8. Above: CFD settings to simulate a binary system. Below: velocity field in the fluid vacuum around two masses. A Lagrange point is in the center of the blue area.

where, in D , $v = \sqrt{GM/a}$ is used, as in Eq. (52). The positive contribution to the precession of perihelia treated in GR is in this way revealed as a phenomenon driven by the shear-thickening vacuum and the mathematical concept of space-time curvature should be replaced, in a quantum theory of gravitation, with the hydrodynamical behavior of such a vacuum, which is specifically a non-Newtonian, dilatant fluid.

IX. Gravitational waves as pressure waves in a fluid vacuum

Being in our model a non-Newtonian dilatant fluid, the vacuum can be treated as a quasi-classical quantum fluid. Quantum-like gravity waves in a classical fluid have been described by Nottale [42]. By resorting to CFD simulations, we modeled a circular domain divided into four sectors: two areas at variable pressure (corresponding to the presence of two masses, which cause an incoming radial flow from the surrounding fluid vacuum) and two walls at fixed pressure (Fig. 8). By letting the domain rotate we simulated the action of a quadrupole in the fluid vacuum. The result is the propagation of negative pressure waves corresponding to gravitational waves, once the currently adopted geometrical explanation of GR is replaced by our

FIG. 9. CFD simulation of gravitational waves as pressure waves in a fluid dilatant vacuum (arbitrary pressure scale). The black dot in the center is structured to mime a binary system in the dilatant vacuum, according to Fig 8

hydrodynamic model. Indeed, if a distant test mass were hit by these negative-pressure waves propagating in the vacuum, it would be expected to exactly reacts as if it were hit by gravitational waves. This because we justify the gravitational force as the Bernoulli force in a fluid vacuum (Sections I, II). The simulation shows gravitational waves as actually the propagation of pressure waves in the vacuum (Fig. 9). Let us consider a supposed space-time deformation as a wave with \times -polarization

$$h_{\times} = -\frac{1}{R} \frac{G^2}{c^4} \frac{4m_1 m_2}{r} (\cos \theta) \sin \left(2\omega \left(t - \frac{R}{c} \right) \right). \quad (60)$$

By replacing G from (17), that is $G = (rP_0/M\rho_0)$, where $M = m_1 + m_2$, and using (34), we see that a gravitational wave is a pressure oscillation propagating through the fluid dilatant vacuum at the speed of light (phonon speed in dilatant vacuum)

$$h_{\times} = -\frac{r}{R} (2P_0 j_0)^2 (m_1 + m_2)^{-1} (\cos \theta) \cdot \sin \left(2 \frac{\sqrt{V_Q}}{r} \left(t - R\sqrt{\rho_0 j_0} \right) \right), \quad (61)$$

whereas the polarization h_+ reads

$$h_+ = -2 \frac{r}{R} (P_0 j_0)^2 (m_1 + m_2)^{-1} (1 + \cos^2 \theta) \cdot \cos \left(2 \frac{\sqrt{V_Q}}{r} \left(t - R\sqrt{\rho_0 j_0} \right) \right), \quad (62)$$

where R is the distance from the observer, t the elapsed time, θ the angle between the perpendicular to the plane of the orbit and the line of sight of the observer, r the radius of the quadrupole, $\sqrt{V_Q}/r = \omega$ its angular frequency, obtained by resorting to the identity (17) in the Newtonian formula for constant angular velocity of a circular orbit $\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}/r^3$ and $\sqrt{\rho_0 j_0}$ corresponds to c^{-1} (34), which accounts for the speed of the gravitational wave as the speed of light, since from our point of view, we observe in both cases pressure waves through the dilatant vacuum, with the difference that in the case of gravitational waves, pressure waves are negative and their frequency is twice the orbital frequency of the binary system. A variation in pressure causes acceleration, acting for example on LIGO's test masses. The Nobel laureate R. Laughlin [43] invites us reflect that: "there is compelling evidence that light and gravity are linked and probably both collective in nature". We believe both arise in the fluid dilatant vacuum, as collective hydrodynamic manifestations of its quanta (pressure waves).

X. Galaxy formation and shapes

When applying the same mechanism also to galaxy formation, we deal with a much lower angular velocity of the black-hole binary system in the galactic core. By varying pressure and angular velocity we obtained different shapes for galaxies. This suggests that also galaxy formation may be driven by pressure gradients in a fluid dilatant vacuum due to a rotating, anisotropic mass distribution, as in a binary system. We can therefore infer that two or more black holes must be present in the galaxy cores [44]. A single supermassive black hole could be responsible for the elliptical shape of galaxies, whereas two or more black holes can generate, as emerged from our simulations, different kinds of spyral galaxies. Importantly, galaxies generated in the dilatant vacuum show to possess a flat profile of the rotation curve, according to observations (film available [45]). This means that neither dark matter nor MOND are necessary to explain the flat profile but it is enough to replace geometrical Einsteinian space-time with a fluid, dilatant vacuum, in which hydrodynamic phenomena driven by pressure and viscosity occur over time, which is relative also in our approach, due to clocks ticking in a more or less viscous vacuum. Indeed, a clock traveling faster through the dilatant vacuum undergoes greater apparent viscosity according to vacuum's rheogram, i.e. to the Lorentz factor 50. In short, GR is a correct quantitative tool but its *qualitative* explanation is wrong: what is currently interpreted as a deformation is actually the action of pressure gradients and viscosity of the dilatant vacuum, as demonstrated in Sect. VIII. By analyzing the different galaxy types showed in Fig. 10, we notice that a weaker pressure gradient, corresponding to less baryon matter in the galaxy core, generates a smaller galaxy: Fig 10 c) represents a dwarf spyral (dS) and letter d) a pea galaxy. In e) we see a grand-design galaxy, whereas in f) an anemic galaxy, obtained by halving the angular velocity of the galaxy. In a spyral galaxy, stars tend to concentrate along the low-pressure corridors (the galaxy arms) in the fluid vacuum, since the latter flows toward the black holes

FIG. 10. CFD simulations of different kinds of galaxies: (a),(b),(c) and (d) represent galaxies at different arbitrary pressure gradients in the fluid vacuum: -100 Pa, -50 Pa, -25 Pa, -11 Pa (respectively). In (e) and (f) pressure is -100 Pa and 45°sectors are used (differently from the 90°sectors showed in Fig. 8). In (f), with respect to (e), representing a *grand-design* galaxy, angular velocity has been halved, so an *anemic* galaxy appears.

situated in the galaxy core. This result of CFD is compatible with the findings presented by D. Christopher Martin, Donald O'Sullivan et al. [46], who described multifilament gas inflows fuelling galaxies: indeed, not only stars but of course also gases can flow along such pressure corridors in the fluid vacuum. The specific black-holes configuration in a core is another element which determines the shape of the galaxy. A 45° configuration (Fig. 10 letter e.) increases the grand-design feature of the galaxy and its size. But when the angular velocity is halved, the grand-design converts into a so-called anemic galaxy. Correct stars migration over time from an arm to another of a spyral galaxy has been also observed in the CFD simulations (Fig. 12). A CFD film showing the birth, the evolution and the behavior (rotation, breath) of a spyral galaxy in dilatant vacuum has been realized by us and it is available at [45].

FIG. 11. Plots showing pressure in the dilatant vacuum along the X-direction of the simulations. The letters of the plots correspond to those of the galaxy shapes in Fig. 10. Animated plots at [45]

FIG. 12. Velocity arrows showing the direction in which stars migrate, along with galactic gases, from an arm to another of a spiral galaxy, due to the warped pressure field in the fluid space.

FIG. 13. To confirm the flat profile of the rotation curve we monitored the angular velocity of some probes at different arbitrary radii (R1 to R13). The positive result highlighting the flat profile is shown in Fig. 14

FIG. 14. Pressure function of angle (for each radius). Since for the considered radii the wavelength is stable with good approximation, a flat profile of rotation velocity is revealed, without resorting to dark matter: the specific hydrodynamic nature of the vacuum as a dilatant fluid is a sufficient condition.

XI. Flat profile without dark matter

The galaxies obtained in our simulations show a flat profile of angular velocity, according to astrophysical observations. This implies that no dark matter is necessary to explain the flat profile: the fact that the vacuum is a dilatant fluid is a sufficient condition. We simulated the motion of probes along concentric orbits in the galaxy, at six different radius values (Fig. 13), to verify the dependence of the rotation velocity on the distance from the galactic core. We confirm (Fig. 14) that the rotation frequency does not vary with distance, implying a flat profile of the rotation curve. This means that,

FIG. 15. Fluid vacuum's velocity field in a spiryal galaxy. Gases flow along these virtual corridors created by the distorsion of the central black holes' gravitational fields induced by galaxy rotation. See also [46]

if the vacuum is a dilatant fluid, there is no need for dark matter. The same can be said for dark energy (about 70% of the universe mass-energy), which is necessary to justify the observed expansion of the universe. In fact in our model dark matter and dark energy are unified, being the medium at stake simply the fluid dilatant vacuum itself (or the fluid dilatant space itself, if one prefers), because it justifies the observed effects of both dark matter (flat-profile, gravitational lensing) and dark energy, since the energy density of the vacuum corresponds to pressure ($J/m^3 = Pa$), causing expansion. For this reason this study and the previous ones [13, 14], which investigate the *specific* nature of physical vacuum as a dilatant fluid, are in our opinion of fundamental importance.

XII. Breath of galaxies

In the video simulation in [45], one can watch the birth, evolution and behavior of a spiryal galaxy in the fluid, dilatant

vacuum. The animated diagram on the right-hand side of the video, shows the persistence of the flat profile of the rotation velocity over time, during the evolution and the life of the galaxy. It is also interesting to see that a *breath* of the galaxy emerges, as pressure waves traveling from the galaxy core cross the galactic disk and continue to propagate through the intergalactic dilatant space. We enlarged the simulation domain enough to check whether the effect could vary and depend on the boundary conditions, but it persisted. We believe this result could be linked to the phenomenon described in [47].

XIII. Conclusion

The theoretical and computational conclusions of this study reinforce the dilatant-vacuum model, suggesting that vacuum dilatancy could be a hydrodynamic property of the Higgs field itself, which is indeed endowed with a certain *viscosity*: if this is the case, we are thence showing that Higgs field also interacts with macroscopic bodies (e.g. with the planet Mercury and the Pioneer probes [13]) and that this ubiquitous fluid is enough to justify the specific rotation of galaxies, without need for dark matter, besides being a key to quantum gravity, by describing the gravitational field as an inflow of dilatant vacuum (of Higgs fluid?) driven by the Bernoulli force produced by spin, as shown in Sect. II. The suggested approach to gravity is compatible with the relativistic effects and vacuum dilatancy also justifies certain specific features of light propagation, such as transverse propagation and the possibility of propagating at very high frequencies. Eventually our CFD simulations show that specific hydrodynamic features of the vacuum might also explain the failure of all ether-drift tests, when a porous medium, such as the Earth's atmosphere, is considered. Studies based on the equations of dilatant vacuum should be therefore continued, also as far as other phenomena and unanswered questions are concerned.

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